

Jeremias L Convocar*

West Visayas State University, Lambunao Campus,
Lambunao, Iloilo, Philippines

Dates: Received: 08 May, 2017; Accepted: 24 May,
2017; Published: 25 May, 2017

*Corresponding author: Jeremias L Convocar,
West Visayas State University, Lambunao
Campus, Lambunao, Iloilo, Philippines, E-mail:
jeremiasconvocar@gmail.com

Keywords: Geopathic stress; Trigger asthma; Staying
over; Moving away

<https://www.peertechz.com>

Research Article

Moving away persons with Asthma from Geopathic Zone (Dowsing Technique): How are they after?

Abstract

No one really knows what exactly caused asthma. However, recent studies revealed that exposure to magnetic fields increases asthma risk and make asthma victims worst. This case study was aimed at determining the extent of the symptoms of asthma among victims when they stayed within and were moved away from the geopathic zone. A combined qualitative-quantitative technique employed the questionnaire checklist, interview, observation, and medical reports in gathering data. Likewise, Y-dowsing rod was used to locate the crossing points of earth grids where geopathic zone is found. The mean was used to describe the extent of the health problems and matrices for the comparison of commonalities, patterns and variances in the analysis and interpretation of qualitative data. The findings revealed that asthma is triggered when one's head and breast is directly exposed within geopathic zone for a longer time. The illness remains incurable or become unresponsive to any medical treatment while the victims stayed within the zone of radiation. However, when one moved away from the said zone it ceases to be a problem. Thus, asthma is a disease of location primarily triggered by geopathic stress and could be effectively addressed when a victim moved away. Unless the people recognized the existence this unseen negative earth energy in selected location and its adverse effect on their health, the exact cause and cure of asthma remained a mystery.

Introduction

Asthma is a common chronic non-communicable disease that affects as many as 334 million people of all ages in all parts of the world [1]. It is a cause of substantial burden to people, often causing a reduced quality of life, not only due to its physical effects, but also its psychological and social effects. The various estimates of its economic burden, mostly due to productivity loss, are all significant. Further, unavoidable asthma deaths are still occurring due to its inappropriate management, including over-reliance on reliever medication rather than preventer medication.

As affirmed, there are no known studies that have successfully unraveled the truth behind the cause of asthma [2,3] and some argued that there is no cure for it [4,5]. However, it was affirmed that exposure to geopathic zone (GZ) that creates energy fields with high positive ion are the primary cause of many of the major health problems [6-8] and known to make asthma victims worse [9,10].

As explained, each human being is a hive of electrochemical activity that generates electricity and an electromagnetic field [11]. The normal resonating frequency in healthy human beings

is 7.8 Hz, which is the same as the normal electromagnetic frequency of earth. Apart from normal electromagnetic fields there are specific points and lines where abnormal frequencies exist due to flow of underground water, Ley lines, Hartmann Lines and Curry Grid. These areas exhibit abnormal electromagnetic activity. In addition, the air is also charged with electricity and has specific activity at certain locations known as GZ in this study.

As reported, GZ are places on the surface of the earth can cause serious health problems for people who stay over them for a long period of time [12,13]. The earth is crisscrossed with invisible grid lines [14], that rise vertically from the groundwater to the surface of the earth and above it, to a distance of 220 km [15]. It exist as a structure of "radiations" rising vertically from the ground like invisible, radioactive wall, each 21 centimeters (9 inches) wide [16] and wherever it crosses (where GZ is located) are seen to be source of potential problems [14,16].

As stated, if a bed or a favorite sitting chair at home or an area at workplace where a person stayed for a long period of time can get very, very uncomfortable [17]. In particular, when person's heads and breast were exposed within GZ they most

likely acquire or develop asthma and other respiratory health problems [6,18]. These energies from earth at specific location have the ability to change the normal body function [19] and detrimental to the health of human body [20]. Moreover, this ability to cause illness in people who spend prolonged periods over them has been scientifically documented in France, Germany [21] and Russia [22].

However, person's reaction to geopathic stress (GS) depends on the intensity of the geopathic situation, term of exposure or the amount of time spent there, heredity, immune system characteristics, parts of their body directly exposed within the said zone of radiation and variety of social reasons and life-style mode of action [18,22,23]. The reactions start with sleeping problems, lack of concentration, a constant state of exhaustion, allergies, migraines, back pain, etc. Under continued stress, a person might experience more serious illnesses such as high blood pressure, diabetes, asthma and chronic skin diseases. Eventually, over a long period of time, with the body's immune system seriously compromised, severe diseases such as cancer can manifest [23].

On the other hand, it was emphasized that in many European countries, Germany and Austria in particular, one of the first questions the doctor may ask is about the location of their bed and how long have they been sleeping there [24]. These questions are routinely asked not only by several thousand doctors, but also many cancer specialist hospitals will recommend a Geopathic Surveyor or Geobiologist as they are often called to investigate their home before deciding on a course of therapy or reaching for the prescription pad. The search, using both dowsing methods (Y-dowsing rod in the case of the present study) to locate geopathic energies and scientific instruments to detect man made electromagnetic energies will determine whether one's illness is linked to GS, electromagnetic stress or both. If so, they will be advised to avoid or eliminate these harmful energies from their home. So they stand a better chance of responding to any treatment given.

Conversely, the most effective way of dealing with geopathic stress (GS) health related problems is to move out one's from staying within the area of GZ [25-27]. However, GS is always neglected and considered as a causal syndrome to ill health and has been always ignored because most of the people are unaware of its occurrence in selected location [28]. Due to their lack of awareness and understanding of the impact electromagnetic fields can have upon their health and wellbeing [29], many suffered from chronic and incurable diseases including asthma which if not properly addressed will end up to unexpected early death.

This study was anchored on various researchers and authorities [9,10,30,31] positions that GS is considered as one major contributing factors and known to make asthma victims worst. Hence, knowing as much as one can about their asthma triggers is important so that they can avoid or minimize exposure to them, making their asthma easier to handle [32].

It is believed that the findings of the present study may further validate the existing theories on the effect of GS on human health particularly on persons with chronic asthma.

Likewise, the result of the investigation may prod health practitioners to recognize GS as a major triggering factor that caused asthma. Moreover, if the assumption is positively proven the result may provide a medical breakthrough in the treatment of asthmatic patients.

Convincingly, the aforesaid insightful concerns and issues lead the researchers to a journey from conventional to a preventive alternative approach by validating the effect of exposure of asthmatic victims from GZ and the extent of their recovery after they were freed from the said zone of radiation.

Does moving asthmatic persons from GZ would help address their chronic asthma health problems? This question must be answered. Hence this study was conducted.

Objectives of the study

The study was aimed at determining the health status of eight purposely and conveniently selected asthma victims while they stayed over and were moved away from the GZ in certain municipalities of the third district of the province of Iloilo, Philippines from year 2014-2016.

Materials and Methods

Research design

This descriptive case study was conducted to compare the asthma health symptoms of eight purposely and conveniently selected study participants while staying within and were moved away from GZ in certain municipalities of the third district of the province of Iloilo, Philippines from year 2014-2016.

The combined quantitative-qualitative approaches in gathering data utilized the interview and observation technique in gathering qualitative data and questionnaire checklist for quantitative data analysis.

Study participants

The samples of eight study participants with chronic asthma were purposely and conveniently chosen by the researcher staying within GZ for a prescribed period of time. The names and other important information about the study participants and proof or records of their asthma health problems were also determined. Further, the asthma victims were evaluated if they met the requirements to qualify as participants of the study.

The specific requirements to qualify as participant of the study are as follows:

1. The specific requirements to qualify as participant of the study are as follows They are staying in sleeping location for at least six hours a day.
2. Their heads and breasts were surveyed directly exposed within GZ.
3. They are permanently or regularly sleeping in bed location for at least two years.
4. They are positively identified by their family members based on their medical reports with chronic asthma health problems.

5. They are willing to follow the advice to move away their bed from within GZ or to sleep in area free from GS.
6. Their location is more accessible to the researcher.

Ethical conduct

The protection of the human subjects is required of all research conducted through the University. The age of the participant were considered. The parents/guardians of the study participants who were of below 18 years of age and those of legal age were provided with an informed consent form, which they were asked to sign and date once they agreed to participate in the study. The form contained information about the purpose and nature of the study, and guaranteed the privacy and confidentiality of each participant. Participants were also advised that they were able to withdraw at any time. Pseudonyms were used in reporting research to protect the anonymity of each participant.

Data gathering technique and instruments

A combined qualitative-quantitative technique in gathering data was used in this case study. The instruments are questionnaire checklist, interview and observation guide, and the Y dowsing rod. Likewise, the availability of medical reports and other potential sources data were also considered.

This study employed the questioning method with the aid of guide questions and interview technique. Guide questions covered the following areas: 1. Personal Information and Medical Reports 2. Asthma related experiences while remained staying within and moved away from within GZ. 3. Other pertinent information.

Quantitative data, materials and instrumentation

The Asthma Symptoms Test: This study utilized slightly modified on-line published symptoms of asthma from various sources [33,34], slightly modified and developed to measure the extent of the symptoms of asthma among victims. The checklist consists of nine items that requires the respondents/participants to encircle the numerical weight corresponding to the selected responses based on frequency of occurrence.

Weight	Description
1	Almost never
2	Infrequently
3	Sometimes
4	Frequently
5	Almost Always

The test were scored by adding, the encircled numbers and interpreted by means of the following scale.

Scale	Description
2.00 and below	No Asthma
2.10 – 3.00	Fairly Experiencing Asthma
3.10 – 4.00	Chronic Asthma
4.10 – 5.00	Severe Asthma

“No Asthma” means that the patients did not experience any symptoms of asthma.

“Fairly Experiencing Asthma” means that the patients are sometimes experiencing asthma symptoms but at tolerable level.

“Chronic Asthma” means that the patients are frequently experiencing earliest asthma symptom that is worsening that requires appropriate treatment.

“Severe Asthma” means that the patient is severely suffering from asthma. The patient is almost always experiencing the signs and requires immediate treatment.

Data analysis

The quantitative data gathered for the study were subjected to certain computer-processed statistics.

Mean: The obtained mean scores were used in describing the extent of asthma symptoms before and after the study participants were freed from GS.

Qualitative data

Interview: The responses in the interview of each study participants using the checklist questionnaire and interview guide were recorded and analyzed to determine the commonalities, patterns and variances before and after they were moved from within GZ. Data from the eight study participants were synthesized to further validate their experiences on the extent of their asthma episodes before and after they were freed from GS.

Observations: The extent of asthma symptoms among study participants were also taken from direct observation of the researcher and close family members or friends of the study participants who had a reliable knowledge about the study participants. The study participants were candidly asked to give their personal experiences and observations on their asthma health problems before and after they were moved from within GZ.

Medical Reports: The medical reports of asthma problems of the study participants before and after they were moved from within GZ were gathered by the researcher and summarized. The frequency of consultation/meeting with the physician, the medical prescriptions and treatment, medical advice, and other pertinent information were also considered. The assistance of the school medical personnel were tapped to further validate the data gathered and appropriateness of terms used in the medical field.

Y-Dowsing Rod: Dowsing is a traditional way of searching underground water stream by various methods [35], and helps identify GS lines and verifying its flow or direction [17]. Along this competence, dowsers have a kind of specifically trained magnetic sense that gives them the ability to detect certain natural fields using dowsing tools [35,36]. In this study, the researcher in his experience as a practicing dowser and an adept researcher in the field of GS utilized Y-dowsing rod in locating GZ.

Professor Benedict explains dowsing as a phenomenon of the combination of Bio-Physics [37]. The bipolar (positive

and negative) sides of the body are closed in an 'emanation stream' through the dowsing rod. The characteristics 'turning of the rod' occurs at the moment the dowser walks over the GZ [38]. Though this technique has been very successful based on its statistical success ratios, and is also simple, fast and inexpensive; there is a continued skepticism as regards its acceptance by the scientific community [39].

Conversely, the main advantage of dowsing (especially in 'multi-level' systems) are cheapness, flexibility, and simplicity of techniques and tools in almost all types of dowsing tools can be 'knock up' in a matter of minutes from things lying around the home or workshop [40]. Likewise, it was affirmed that many doctors in Germany, Austria and France used dowsers with the aid of dowsing tool in their health programs [12]. This was confirmed that inside GZ copper L-rod got deflected [35]. Notably, experts tried many instruments, some are very expensive, but none has proved as consistent, reliable and accurate or as quick as human dowser. All scientists measuring GS with instruments will take a dowser along to locate the radiation initially [41].

The Y-shaped rod used in the present study dates from dowsing's beginnings and remains quite popular among modern practitioners [42]. The rod is made of two bamboo splints as handle attached to Y-shaped guava twig was developed and used by the researcher/dowser in locating the crossing of earth grids where GZ is found. The dowser holds on both ends of forks of the Y with the long opposite end pointing forward. Exercising a slight outward pull on the forks of the Y to keep the end under tension, the dowser steadily walks over the area in the regular grid pattern, carefully covering the entire area of the bed and its surroundings to be searched. When the dowser passes over the earth grids, the rod points down showing the direction of grid lines and eventually the crossing point of knot where the GZ is found [43]. Likewise, monitoring the movements of these dowsing tools leads and reveals the places where GS is strongest [44]. The researcher marks the spot and review the survey until the center of the crossing earth grids and the scope of GZ is finally located. Finally, the drawing or graphical presentation showing the bed position, parts of body exposed (head and breast) while lying on bed, and the spot for the crossing point and scope of GZ were also prepared as bases in conceptualizing the scope of GZ among study participants.

Data Gathering Procedure: Letter of permission was secured from the University President, Campus Administrator, local community authorities, parents' of asthma victims, and concerned study participants.

The researchers personally visited, interviewed, and observed the study participants with the assistance of their family members or close relatives or friends who have direct knowledge of the health problems. Likewise, the researchers assist the study participants and their family members in the filling up of the questionnaires and personally initiated the conduct the interviews and observations following the interview and observation guide.

The data gathered were tape recorded, reviewed and presented in a matrix to establish common experiences and extent of symptoms of asthma among victims while they remained exposed and after they moved away from within the GZ. Likewise, photographs and other additional information about the study participants were also taken to substantiate the existing data as basis for analysis and interpretation.

Data analysis

The following data analysis procedures were employed in the determining the common experiences and extent of the cause of asthma among victims while they remained exposed and were moved away from within GZ:

1. Preparation and formulation of analysis matrices, taking into consideration of the parts of their body directly exposed within the GZ and the categories or units of analysis.
2. Encoding of narrative data from interview, observation and medical reports and other pertinent data in their respective cells in the matrix.
3. Examination of the narrative data in the cells to find out common themes, patterns and variances.
4. Establishment of synthesis based on the commonalities and patterns as well as variances for derivation of findings.
5. Construction of value categories and then abstracting from findings and corresponding conclusion in response to the intent of the study.

Results

This case study was conducted to compare the common experiences and extent of the asthma episodes among eight purposely and conveniently selected study participants while they remained exposed within and were moved away from within GZ during the year 2014-2016 in a certain municipalities of the province of Iloilo, Philippines.

This combined quantitative-qualitative approach utilized the interview and observation technique in gathering the qualitative data and questionnaire checklist for the quantitative data.

Case No. 1 – Severe Asthma

Pito, 72 years old and a father of five, transferred to their new house in one of the remote barrios of Sta. Barbarra, Iloilo, Philippines. In their early years of staying in new bed location, Pito started to experience unusual health problems like insomnia, nightmares, feeling fatigue, back pains, bloated stomach and high blood. He cannot understand why he had an episodes of coughing especially at night, shortness of breath, feeling very weak while walking, feeling tired, easily upset, and grouchy (Table 1). Likewise, he is always clamoring that he cannot walk too far because he felt that as if his two hands were carrying a two big of cups full of water. He brought

the health problems to a physician and he was diagnosed with chronic asthma. Further, he was given some doses for maintenance, inhalers for use in severe cases and advised to have a regular monthly check up. However, as the years go by, despite continues treatment and medication, Pito's asthma health problems remained incurable and even becoming worst. Because of uncontrolled asthma episodes and intolerable health problems, his life is becoming more miserable. The wife and children were so worried and greatly affected of Pito's failing health conditions and the intolerable expenses for the daily treatment and maintenance.

Unexpectedly, the researcher heard about the disturbing health problems as per conversation via electronic media from the family members calling abroad to verify the status of the health status of their father.

Year 2014, the researcher visited the family and shared his

knowledge on the adverse effect of GS on human health and how it could be avoided. With the consent and support of the family, the conduct of the survey of GZ location was done and it was found out that the upper half parts of Pito's body (head and breast) was directly exposed within GZ (Figure 1). Right away, the transfer of Pito's bed to GS free location was done to address the problems. Later, it was noticed that in Pito's new GS free bed's location, the long recurring and deteriorating asthma health problems gradually disappeared (Table 2) despite without treatment or medication. As he said, "I could now sleep better, seldom having a nightmare, woke up in the morning with restored energy, and do some works at home and even walk at a distance without worrying of unusual fatigue". Further he exclaimed, "I'm OK!", "I felt much better than before!" If there were sometimes besetting health problems like colds, fatigue, coughing, and high blood, he considered it as normal to his age as a result of overwork, food intake, and

Table 1: Frequency of Occurrence and Extent of Asthma Symptoms While Staying Within GZ.

Asthma Related Experiences	Frequency of Occurrence/Extent of Asthma Symptoms							
	Study Participants/Case No.							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Coughing, especially at night.	4	4	4	5	4	5	5	4
2. Losing breath easily/Shortness of breath	5	4	5	5	4	4	5	4
3. Difficulty talking or concentrating	4	4	4	4	3	4	4	4
4. Feeling very tired or weak when exercising	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	5
5. Wheezing or coughing after exercise	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	4
6. Feeling irritable, easily upset, grouchy, moody	5	3	4	4	3	4	4	5
7. Signs of colds or allergies (sneezing, runny nose, cough, nasal congestion, sore throat, and headache)	4	3	3	5	3	4	4	4
8. Trouble sleep/Nightmares	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Others: Bloating stomach/Back Pains	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Mean	4.55	3.88	4.11	4.44	3.66	4.22	4.44	4.22
Description	SA	CA	SA	SA	CA	SA	SA	SA

Legend:

A. Frequency of Occurrence		B. Extent of Asthma	
Weight	Description	Scale	Description
5	Almost Always	4.10 – 5.00	SA - Severe Asthma
4	Frequently	3.10 – 4.00	CA - With Chronic Asthma
3	Sometimes	2.10 – 3.00	FEA - Fairly Experiencing Asthma
2	Infrequent	2.00 and below	NA - No Asthma
1	Almost Never		

Case No. 1 – Severe Asthma

Length of Stay Within GZ: 10 years
Parts of Body Directly Exposed: Head & Breast
Occupation: Farming
Civil Status: Married Age: 72

Figure 1: Pito's Parts of Body Exposed and GZ.

sudden change of climate. However, “I could easily recover and regain my normal health condition”.

Case No. 2 – Asthma with Pneumonia

Edmar, 13 years old, the younger of the two children, had been diagnosed with pneumonia at age six by the time her mother placed him in bed exposed within GZ (Figure 2). At age 10 when he permanently slept in the geopathically stressed bed, he began to experience recurrent episodes of troublesome cough and wheeze at night, breathlessness, feeling very tired while walking or playing, and feeling grouchy (Table 1). His classmates sometimes noticed that he had a red eye bags, appeared weak, and non-participative in any school activities. Later, his health problem was brought to the physicians for checkup and he was found with chronic asthma. Doses like the

use antidotes and nebulizer were advised to be used in severe moments. However, it was noticed that despite continuous treatment and medications he underwent yet asthma episodes becomes severe. Likewise, tardiness, frequent absences and drowsiness in attending classes were also observed.

Year 2015, a survey of the presence of GS was done in the sleeping location of Edmar and it was confirmed that his head and breast is within the GZ (Figure 2). With the consent of his mother, Edmar was transferred to a sleeping location away from GZ. As observed by the family, and as testified by Edmar, his asthma health problems gradually disappeared (Table 2). He was able to sleep well at night and woke up in the morning with energy and eagerness in doing school activities and tasks. As he said, “I could now run farther without coughing and wheezing and enjoying playing games with my peers without worrying

Table 2: Frequency of Occurrence and Extent of Asthma Symptoms After Moved Away from Within GZ.

Asthma Related Experiences	Frequency of Occurrence/Extent of Asthma							
	Study Participants/Case No.							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Coughing, especially at night.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2. Losing breath easily/Shortness of breath	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2
3. Difficulty talking or concentrating	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
4. Feeling very tired or weak when exercising	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5. Wheezing or coughing after exercise	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6. Feeling tired and irritable, easily upset, grouchy, moody	2	1	2	2	1	1		1
7. Signs of colds or allergies (sneezing, runny nose, cough, nasal congestion, sore throat, and headache)	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
8. Trouble sleep /Nightmares	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Others: Bloating stomach/Back Pains	3	1	1	2	1	2	1	1
Mean	1.88	1	1.44	1.22	1	1.11	1	1.11
Description	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Legend:

A. Frequency of Occurrence		B. Extent of Asthma	
Weight	Description	Scale	Description
5	Almost Always	4.10 – 5.00	SA - Severe Asthma
4	Frequently	3.10 – 4.00	CA - With Chronic Asthma
3	Sometimes	2.10 – 3.00	FEA - Fairly Experiencing Asthma
2	Infrequent	2.00 and below	NA - No Asthma
1	Almost Never		

Case No. 2 – Asthma with Pneumonia

Length of Stay within GZ: 2 years
 Parts of Body Directly Exposed: Head and Breast
 Occupation: N.A. (Student)
 Civil status: N.A. (Minor) Age: 12

Figure 2: Edmar’s Parts of Body Exposed and GZ.

of feeling very tired". "No more wheezing or coughing in spite of my long and tiresome activities". "I'm almost OK in my new sleeping location". According to his mother, if there were some health problems that may occur, it is usually attributed to sudden change of climate but he can easily recover.

Case No. 3 – Relapsing Asthma

Kerwin, 29 years old, married with one daughter transferred to their new house in one of the barrios of the municipality Badiangan, province of Iloilo, Philippines. Due to access in watching TV at night, they just slept in the area of living room adjacent to their dining and kitchen. At the start, Kerwin's noticed that he began to experience unusual fatigue, frequent coughing especially at night, difficulty in talking or concentrating, trouble sleep, bloated stomach, and chronic fatigue and later diagnosed with asthma (Table 1). His wife noticed that despite treatment, use of nebulizer, and other possible remedies, his asthma health problem becomes chronic. Due to such deteriorating health problems, he decided to stop working and just stay at home for rest and health recovery. His wife is very much worried of his recurrent episodes of wheezing and breathlessness while sleeping at night. In serious cases, he was compelled to use of nebulizer and even admitted to hospital. Other means to remedy the health problems were also tried including the service of quack doctor but of no positive effect. However, with the request of his wife, the researcher conducted a survey of the sleeping location of Kerwin with the assumption that the asthma health problem might be attributed to GS. It was confirmed that Kerwin's head and breast were unluckily exposed within the GS zone (Figure 3). Likewise, an advised to transfer to GS free sleeping location was done in order to address the problem immediately. Since the time when Kerwin was moved away from within GZ, his asthma health problems gradually disappeared (Table 2). As he said, "unconsciously, I regained my energy, woke up in the

morning in good mood, sleep well at night and my wheezing and coughing just disappeared". I went back to my work in the farm like harvesting rice and assisting in mango fruit bearing project, drive motorcycle for extra income without experiencing anymore the unusual fatigue.

However after one year, his wife went abroad and left Kerwin and her daughter thinking that everything is alright. Without the wife's knowledge, Kerwin transferred to new sleeping location not knowing that it is also exposed within GZ (Figure 4). Due to such exposure, his previous asthma health problems recurred and compelled him again to use the nebulizer in severe cases and sought the help of the physician.

Unexpectedly, the researcher visited the place to monitor his health status and it was confirmed that Kerwin is sleeping again within geopathically stressed area (Figure 4). Thus, Kerwin's asthma attacked was attributed to the re-exposure of his head and breast within GZ. After he was moved away from the zone of radiation, the health problem ceased and eventually regained his normal health condition. As he said, "next time, I should be careful of the place where to sleep." Further, he explained that it's normal sometimes to have a cough, colds, feel tired due to over work and sudden change in climate, but I could easily recover after rested.

Case No. 4 - Recurring Asthma

Lisa, 13 years old, the eldest daughter of the three children, had been diagnosed with asthma health problem by the time she transferred to new bed location in their newly renovated house. According to their parents, since birth, and until Lisa reaches the age of eight, this kind of health problem was not noticed. Subsequently, in her new bed location, she frequently experience coughing at night, losing of breath, feeling very tired while having some physical activities including recurrent episodes of wheeze and allergies (Table 1). Likewise, an episode

Case No. 3 – Relapsing Asthma

Length of Stay Within GZ: 2 years
Parts of Body Directly Exposed: Head and Breast
Occupation: Farm assistant
Civil status: Married Age: 29

Figure 3: Parts of Body Exposed and Location GZ.

of sleepless nights and woke up late in the morning, sleep talking, difficulties to concentrate, and always irritable even without reasons were also observed. Further, she is always complaining of extreme fatigue when backed home from school and after participated in some school activities. As a consequence, the health problems also resulted to tardiness in attending classes and absenteeism. Due to such disturbing episodes, the health problem was brought to the physician and diagnosed with asthma health problems. Likewise, doses of antidotes were prescribed by the physician to treat her allergy, coughing and wheezing after the examination. However, it was noticed that for a period of four years, in spite of regular treatment or medication, Lisa's asthma health problem remained incurable and even getting worst. Eventually, the health problems created much worries and concerns to the family.

Year 2015, the researcher visited their house, and shared the information about the link of GS to her asthma health problem. A survey was done on upper double deck bed, and it was confirmed that Lisa's head and breast were directly exposed within GZ (Figure 5). Right away, the advice to move away from within the GZ was done. Later, It was observed, that for a year of Lisa's staying in the house of her Aunt free from GS the asthma health problem gradually disappeared. According to her parents, unknowingly Lisa's asthma symptoms ceased. Likewise, they noticed that her frequent coughing at night, wheezing, shortness of breath and other asthma health

problems stopped (Table 2) when she stayed away from her stressed bed.

However, every time when she went back home and returned to her stressed bed for a considerable period of time, Lisa's asthma health problems recurred. Ultimately, the father decided to make an adjustment of her bed location away from GZ, and Lisa's asthma health problem didn't recur anymore.

Case No. 5 - Persistent Asthma

Eman, 9 years old, the second of the three children, slept below the double deck bed with her older sister Lisa. Likewise, he was having similar episodes of asthma health problems with his sister when they transferred to their new bed location. According to their parents, since his birth, until the age of five, they did not notice this kind of health problems. However, later in the new bed location, the parents observed symptoms like coughing at night, shortness of breath, always feeling very tired, and wheezing (Table 1). Due to troubled sleep at night caused by asthma attack, Eman woke up late in the morning, feeling fatigue, and even irritable that resulted to tardiness and absenteeism in school. Likewise, he complained of unusual fatigue when get involved in school activities. The health problem was brought to the physician and he was diagnosed with chronic asthma. Some treatments and advice were given by the physician to address his health problem, yet it was

Case No. 4 -Recurring Asthma

Length of Stay within GZ: 2 years
Parts of Body Directly Exposed: Head and Breast
Occupation: N.A. (Student)
Civil status: N.A. (Minor) Age: 12

Figure 4: Kerwin's Parts of Their Bodies Exposed and Location of GZ in the Living Area.

Case No. 5 -Persistent Asthma

Length of Stay within GZ: 3 years
Parts of Body Directly Exposed: Head & Breast
Occupation: Teaching Sex: Male
Civil Status: Married Age: 46

Figure 5: Lisa's Parts of Body Exposed and GZ.

noticed that his asthma remained incurable and even getting worst.

Year 2015, the researcher visited their house, and shared the information about the possible link of GS to the asthma health problem of their son. A survey was done, and it was found out that Eman's head and breast were also directly exposed within GZ (Figure 5). The advice to move away from within the GZ was given and observed. For a year of Eman's stayed in the house of his Aunt free from GZ the asthma health problem gradually disappear. Moreover, it was noticed by Eman's parents that the asthma health problems stopped despite without medication. The coughing at night, shortness of breath and other asthma health related problems also ceased (Table 2).

However, every time Eman went home with her sister Lisa and slept in their geopathically stressed bed, Eman's and Lisa's asthma health problems recurred.

Case No. 6 - Persistent Asthma

Gingging, 44 years old, a mother of seven children, started to experience unusual health problems when she transferred with her husband and youngest son in their new sleeping location after their house was renovated (Figure 6). She can't understand why in their new bed she frequently had coughing at night, losing breath, difficulty in talking, feeling very tired after doing her jobs at school or at home, irritable, sneezing and runny nose, trouble sleep, bloated stomach and back pains (Table 1). Due to such disturbing occurrence, the health problem was brought to the physician, and she was diagnosed with chronic asthma. A prescription with the use of antidote (prolix, 3x day) and nebulizer in serious cases were given by the physician. However, she noticed that for three years, despite the use of conventional treatment, her asthma health problems remained incurable and even becoming worst. She felt uncomfortable and irritable most of the time because of unexplained severe fatigue and drowsiness she experience after she performed some of the tasks or activities at home or at work. As she said, "I almost always felt very tired or exhausted at the end of the day".

Year 2015, when the researcher heard about the health problem, then she was advised to move away from GS zone. A survey was done in their bed room and it was found out that in their bed location, Gingging's and her son's upper parts of body were directly exposed within the area of GZ (Figure 6). Based on the findings, she was advised to transfer to a sleeping location not affected by GS.

Later, Gingging was asked about her health status, and she noticed that there are times she felt not feeling well especially in the school. Although she was freed from exposure in the GZ in her house, but every time she reported and stayed in the school, she always felt very tired, drowsy, and almost feeling exhausted at the end of the day. To verify the possible source of her uncomfortable experience, a survey of GS at the office where she is always staying was done. Likewise, it was found out that table where she is always staying is exposed within the area of GZ. To address her health problem, a moving of the table away from GZ was done.

Since the time Gingging transferred to new bed location and seats free from GS she noticed that her asthma health problems gradually disappeared. Her frequent coughing, wheezing, breathlessness, trouble sleep and other asthma health problems just fade away even without treatment (Table 2). As she said, "I woke up early in the morning refreshed, in good mood, did my job with energy, and ended the day feeling alright". "It is such a great thing to save our budget for my daily health maintenance and treatment." If sometimes I have a cough, colds or fatigue, it is due to sudden climate change and over work, but I can easily recover". "I'm so thankful and happy because I regained my normal health condition."

Case No. 7. Persistent Asthma

Matt, 5 years old, the youngest of the seven children, started to experience unusual health problems by the time he slept with her mother and father in their new bed location (Figure 6). His parents noticed that Matt's chronic episodes of coughing at night, recurrent breathlessness and wheeze is deteriorating since the time they stayed in their new sleeping location (Table 1). Pieces of towels were always prepared and

Case No. 6. Persistent Asthma

Length of Stay within GZ: 3 years
Parts of Body Directly Exposed: Head & Breast
Occupation: Teaching Sex: Female
Civil Status: Married Age: 46

Figure 6: Gingging's Parts of Body Exposed and GZ (Office).

Case No. 7. Persistent Asthma

Length of Stay within GZ: 3 years

Parts of Body Directly Exposed: Head and Breast

Occupation: N.A. (Student)

Sex: Male

Civil status: N.A. (Children)

Age: 5

Figure 7: Gingging's Parts of Body Exposed and GZ (Home).

utilized because of frequent back sweating. He was consulted to the health physician and diagnosed with chronic asthma. According to his mother Gingging, "we don't have this kind of health problems before, however when we were sleeping in this sleeping location, our asthma just arise". Due to persistent asthma attack to his son, a monthly consultations observed, treatments of antidotes (Weptin or prolix for asthma and Alnix for cold and allergy) were regularly taken in, and the use of nebulizer in severe cases. The parents were very much worried of the asthma of their son because it appears that for a period of three years despite continuous treatment and medication the asthma health problem of their son remained incurable and even getting worst. According to his mother, "if we only gathered the empty packs or bottles of medicine we purchased and placed it in sack, and consider the amount we spent, I can't imagine the hassle brought to our life".

During the time when their sleeping location was surveyed, it was also found out that Matt's upper parts of body were also exposed within GZ (Figure 7). Right away, a relocation was done (free from GS), and great improvements in the health condition of Matt was also observed. The long recurring asthma health problems gradually disappeared. Unusual coughing, breathlessness, wheezing, and troubled sleep also ceased. Matt able to sleep well at night, woke normally in the morning, participate in outdoors games and activities without any indication of wheezing and coughing. Obviously, Matt recovered his health and enjoyed childhood normal life. His mother Gingging said "no more extra budget for asthma treatment and medicine". According to Matt's parents, "Matt's now is very much OK, and we are very much happy about it". "We are so thankful of knowing that there are such places when we stay for a length of time will greatly affect our health".

Case No. 8. Severe Asthma with Pneumonia

Nene, the older of the two daughters, started to experience unusual health problems since the time she slept with her sister in new bed location. She usually woke up late in the morning because of troublesome cough at night, recurring episodes of wheeze and breathlessness, sleep walking, back pains, and

bloated stomach (Table 1). Likewise, her mother noticed of her sleep walking, daytime fatigue, difficult to concentrate and felt so exhausted at the end of the day. Her health problem was brought to the physicians and was diagnosed with chronic asthma. Doses of antibiotics were provided for seven days with an inhaler to control the persistent episodes of severe asthma attack. However, despite treatments, achieving asthma control is still an unmet need for Nene. Due to deteriorating health condition, additional checkup was required including x-ray laboratory and she was found out positive of pneumonia. These miserable moments of Nene's life brought much worries and concerns to her mother.

The problem reached to the attention of the researcher, and the scheduled visit was done with the consent and support of her mother. It was discovered that after the survey of GS zone, it was found out that for a period of seven years Nene's head and breast were directly exposed within the GZ (Figure 8). Immediately, the relocation of Nene's bed to GS free location was done. Later, her mother noticed that the persistent asthma episodes of her daughter gradually disappeared. Nene said, "Unknowingly the chronic asthma symptoms that I experienced just vanished away." After months of her recovery, she actively joined school and barrio's sports activities and festivities without any indications of unusual fatigue. As her mother exclaimed, "What a great help because we don't spend money for her medicine and maintenance". "She is now almost normal, and I'm very happy about the positive changes that happened in her life". Further her mother said that if there were some health problems that may arise like coughing, colds, or fatigue, it's just normal because of the sudden change of climate, result of too much physical activity, but she can easily recover."

Discussion

While staying within GZ

Generally, the study participants claimed that they started to have asthma health problem by the time they stayed in their new beds location (exposed over zone). This finding implies

Case No. 8. Severe Asthma with Pneumonia

Length of stay Within GZ: 7 years
Parts of body Directly Exposed: Head & Breast
Occupation: N.A. (Student) Sex: Female
Civil Status: Single Age: 17

Figure 8: Parts of body Exposed and Location of GZ.)

that asthma is triggered when one's head or breast is exposed within GZ for a considerable period of time. As argued, long-term exposure to GZ can cause bronchial asthma [45]. There is a release of certain chemical substances (histamine, and acetylcholine) within the lung tissue which in turn cause bronchial muscle to spasm, increased bronchial secretions, and swelling of bronchial tubes. In this stage, symptoms can occur within five or more years and associated with a high risk for serious cardiac events and complete suppression of the immune system. Stress hormones that act on the heart, blood vessels, and lungs may contribute to heart diseases, high blood pressure and asthma.

It was explained that GS are referred to earth or electromagnetic radiation or electro-magnetic fields [20,46], that produced detrimental effects in humans. The maximum conductivity (known within GZ) corresponds to the position of the active strips that influenced air ionization over the zone as well as the flow of air and ground currents [7]. The positive ions are concentrated in vertical emission zones and have been detected even high up in apartment blocks [47]. A negative spin that causes a negative effect in the body produces high level of stress that comes on unseen – one can't see it, hear it, smell it, or taste it – unless they are clairvoyant or sensitive [17]. Further, it was clarified by several researchers and health authorities [46,48] that exposure to GZ that creates energy fields with high positive ions may decreased pulmonary performance and exacerbate allergic asthma symptoms and other respiratory irritations and problems [6,30,49]. Thus, the findings may suggest the linked of positive ion (from within GZ) on asthma symptoms and other respiratory health problems of the study participants.

It was also stressed that wherever two rays cross, a "Hartman Knot" (where geopathic point or zone is found) constitute much of a health hazard including heart and circulatory problems, high blood, tuberculosis and asthma [26], when passed directly through the breast area of the body in the bed site [18]. Thus, the findings may also suggest for the awareness of the public of the existence of GZ in certain location and its adverse effect on human health.

Further, it was explained that ions (in the case of GS) are microscopic particles that carry an electric charge [50]. In air, ions are created when enough energy acts upon molecules of air and displace an electron which attaches to a nearby stable molecule that gets a negative charge. The molecule that loses an electron becomes a positive ion. Air molecules are broken apart by cosmic radiation, radio activity in soil, ultraviolet radiation, lightening, moving air flow friction, friction caused by air-borne sand and dirt, and falling water, etc. Hence, GS may be a form of imbalanced electromagnetic energy spectrum or subtle energy [51], linked to high positive ion [48], that is harmful to living organisms [15] and may eventually cause or triggered asthma when one's head or breast is exposed within the geopathic structure for a considerable length of time.

Likewise, it was affirmed that when oxygen (in GZ) is reabsorbed via the lung alveoli, the ionized molecules are taken up like the normal oxygen molecules and pass into the blood corpuscles [52]. The red blood corpuscles whose hemoglobin is oxygenated by the air during inspiration, receives also the ionized oxygen. The negative charge is carried throughout the body, whereas the positive charge may attack the blood platelets (thrombocytes) which in sensitive patients release their irritating hormone, serotonin.

It is this powerful and versatile neurohormone, serotonin which is responsible for many of the unpleasant symptoms exhibited by persons breathing positively ionized, air. In effect, they were being poisoned by their own serotonin, causing: migraines, hot flashes, irritability, pains around the heart, difficulty in breathing and a worsening of bronchial complaints, anxiety and irrational tension, lack of concentration, constant state of exhaustion, allergies, etc [53]. Nevertheless, under continued stress, a person might experience more serious illnesses such as high blood pressure, diabetes, asthma, including severe diseases such as cancer [23].

On the basis of these facts, it seems reasonable to postulate that positive air ions (attributed to exposure within GZ) are 'serotonin releasers' and that a local accumulation of serotonin

in the trachea. As a consequence, the positive ionization of blood increased its serotonin release that significantly caused or triggered asthma and other respiratory health problems among study participants.

The findings revealed that the study participants showed varied reactions as to the severity of their asthma health problems while they remained exposed within GZ. In the case of Lisa and Eman, although they have similar geopathic exposure, the extent of effect revealed that Lisa was severely affected by asthma than Eman. This finding may imply that the effect of GS on human health is contingent on genetic and environmental factors that interact and play an important role in the development of asthma. As explained, person's reaction to GS depends on the intensity of the geopathic situation, term of exposure or the amount of time spent there, heredity, immune system characteristics, parts of their body directly exposed within the said zone of radiation and variety of social reasons and life-style mode of action [18,22,23]. Reactions start with sleeping problems, lack of concentration, a constant state of exhaustion, allergies, migraines, back pain, etc. Under continued stress, a person might experience more serious illnesses such as high blood pressure, diabetes, asthma and chronic skin diseases. Eventually, over a long period of time, with the body's immune system seriously compromised, severe diseases such as cancer can manifest [23]. Hence, the findings may suggest that the severity of person's asthma symptoms that sit in is dependent on the intensity of the geopathic situation, the amount of time spent there, and the nature and parts of human body directly exposed.

It was also found out that majority of the study participants testified that they frequently experience the recurrent episodes of wheeze, breathlessness, troublesome coughing especially at night, difficulty to concentrate, debilitating tiredness or wheezing after some physical activities, feeling irritable, colds or allergies, back pains, bloated stomach, nightmares, etc. by the time they transferred to their new bed location (exposed over GZ). As stated, asthma is an allergic state in which the bronchial tubes constrict the passage of air, resulting in severe difficulty breathing and whistling type of exhalation [54]. The sides of airways in the lungs become thick and swollen, causing recurring episodes of wheezing, breathlessness, tightness and aching of the chest, and throat constriction-like sensations. Sufferers often have a persistent cough that lasts for more than a week or coughing attacks after laughing, crying, brisk-walking, or exercising. Some people wake up in the middle of the night coughing or wheezing, especially between 3 a.m. and 5 a.m., the lung meridian time.

Moreover, it was argued that spending long periods of time over a detrimental area produces a stress reaction in the human body. This is the same as stress produced by any other means [55]. The effect is gradual, involving a slow deterioration in health. Due to such exposure, often the victims may not be able to get to sleep or they wake frequently or suffer from strange dreams, feeling cold, sleep walking, grinding of teeth and wake up feeling tired and irritable including resistance to conventional or alternative treatment [14,15,55]. These indicators were also validated by the findings of the present

study among study participants when their heads and breast were exposed within GZ.

Furthermore, due to such exposure, often the study participants may not be able to get to sleep or they wake frequently or suffer from strange dreams and wake up feeling tired and irritable [57,56]. Other indications includes insomnia, restless sleep, feeling cold, sleep walking, grinding of teeth and nightmares, asthma and respiratory difficulties at night [58]. These findings may suggest of the common symptoms or experiences when one stayed for a considerable length of time over the GZ.

Moreover, it was also found that despite continuous treatment and medication the asthma health problem among study participants remained incurable and even getting worst while they stayed with their heads and breast exposed within GZ. This finding may indicate the complete insensitivity of patients to any kind of treatment when they are affected by GS.

These observations were supported by findings of previous studies [15,59], that until a person are taken off within the geopathic structures their capacity to heal is greatly impaired. Conversely, GS does not cause an illness, but lowers one's immune system, so they have less chance of fighting any illness. It prevents one's body properly absorbing vitamins, minerals, trace elements etc. from your food (and supplements) and often making one allergic to food, drinks and environmental pollution [15].

According to Dr. Hartmann, one of the first things to be adversely affected by GS was the immune system [60]. As a result of this, individuals placed above an area of geopathic disturbance soon lost the capacity to defend themselves against harmful bacteria that previously they were able to withstand. Further, it can undermine both the body's subtle energy system (the etheric body, chakras and meridians) and the body's electrical system (brain, heart and muscles), thus delaying healing and recovery [28].

Conversely, when persons' respiratory system is affected by GS, asthma and other respiratory tract infections problems may sit in, become unresponsive to any medical treatment and even make asthma health problems worst. Thus, the findings may suggest that as long as the person's body is affected by GS their capacity to recover from ailments is impaired.

Furthermore, the findings also revealed the bloating of stomach and other digestive system problems experienced by study participants while they stayed within GZ. As explained exposure to GZ have effects on the digestive system [11]. Disease of the stomach and intestines are often linked to GS because the blood has to leave these organs and move to muscles. Prolonged GS (2-3 years) can disrupt the digestive system, irritating the large intestine and cause diarrhea, constipation, cramping, and bloating. This happens because stress hormones slow the release of stomach acid and emptying of the stomach. Thus, the findings suggest on the possible disease of the stomach and intestines when person stayed within the zone of disturbance for considerable length of time.

Moreover, it was noticed that due to lack of awareness or knowledge among study participants, family members, and medical practitioners about the occurrence of GZ in certain location and its adverse effect on human health, asthma becomes severe and incurable. However, the positive and negative effects of earth radiation on our body are often forgotten, ignored or simply unknown [61]. Earth rays are mostly natural underground water veins that are responsible for around 95% of geological stress to human health. Awareness can lead to action to resolve the problem by removing himself from the zone to bring vast improvement in their health [28]. Hence, the findings may imply that unless the people acknowledge the existence of this noxious energy in specific location, the exact cause and cure of asthma will remain a mystery.

When moved away from GS Zone

The findings revealed that when the study participants moved away from within GZ, their long recurring and persistent asthma health problems gradually disappeared. Likewise, it was noticed that the victims regained their normal health conditions despite without medication or treatment. As they said “my health problems unknowingly disappeared, and now I’m almost normal”. They were able to sleep well at night and woke up in the morning with regenerated energy. Some other health problems that arise later were allegedly attributed to other factors like food intake, climate change and overwork, but they can easily recover.

The findings may validates the linked of long exposure of one’s head or breast within geopathic zone to asthma and other respiratory health problems. These observations was supported by Carstens [62], published study documenting the spontaneous healing of 700 terminal cancer patients after they relocated their beds to an area free from geopathic stress. Carstens explains that the body has great self-healing potential, which if it can be tapped into by treating the root cause of an illness rather than its symptoms. Thus, the findings of the study may call for the freeing asthma patients from being nexposed within GZ to effectively address the health problems.

Likewise, the findings affirmed seven year study (1988–1995) in Germany [59], that showed that until a person was taken off the Geopathic structure, their capacity to heal was greatly impaired and may lead to dangerous diseases [63], since the illness is considered as a problem of location [64].

These finding implies that the only road to recovery for the person who is suffering from asthma is to stay away or avoid GS. It’s like any sickness that the root cause must be eliminated in order for the patient to fully recover. Conversely, any medication will not help a person if they continuously stay or expose their heads and breasts within GZ. Hence, moving away from exposure over GS zone is the simplest, practical and effective way to treat a person with chronic asthma.

Conversely, the primary and the most effective way of dealing with GS is moving one’s bed. The farther the bed can be moved, the likely it is that one gets out of the stressed area.

However, moving a bed by a little as two feet is sometimes sufficient to get out of the stressed area as it can be localized [27].

Thus, the findings call for the awareness of the public on the adverse effect of GS on their health and how it could be avoided. Unless the victim will stay away from exposure within GZ their asthma health problems will remain incurable and may become worse. However, when they moved away from the said zone of radiation, the said problem will just disappear.

Furthermore, the findings affirmed the importance of a sleeping environment free from geopathic and electromagnetic interference and radiation fields [38]. Many doctors in Germany, Austria and France used dowsers with aid of dowsing tool in their health care programs. Indeed, many of them undertake personally. Several of the authoritative figures from the history of dowsing were in fact, medical dowsers, for example, Dr. Curry, who discovered the existence of the dangerous network of earth lines named after him [12].

Moreover, the findings of this study may serve as a challenge to all health-care professionals who are dedicated to the development of holistic care to further their understanding and awareness of this phenomenon [28]. Awareness can lead to action to resolve the problem by removing himself from the zone to bring vast improvement in their health [11]. Thus, the findings may suggest for the strengthening of public awareness on the existence of GS, its adverse effect on their health and how could it be avoided.

Finally, it was affirmed that we are dwelling in detail in the GZ problem because it is very important for practical medicine [65]. If a patient receives therapy and then he comes home to find himself in dangerous GZ (e.g., in the bedroom), all efforts of doctor to cure him would be useless. That naturally would compromises the authority of doctor and his method of therapy, while actually detrimental factor would be associated with the GZ in the patient’s home. Hence, the findings may suggest that doctors should work in close cooperation with the specialists in biological geophysics or dowsers, who are able to detect the dangerous GZ in the patient’s homes.

Although the present study has been useful in determining the extent of the asthma symptoms while the victims stayed over and were moved away from GZ, several limitations existed. This combined qualitative-quantitative case study is primarily limited to the observations and experiences of the study participants and close family members using in depth interview, observation and checklist and researchers’ dowsing ability in locating the crossing points of earth grids where GZ is found. As such does not precisely gauge the exact amount of positive ion or geopathic/electropathic radiation. Radiation is subtle that they cannot be measured by means of unusual measuring devices that work according to scientific physical principle [66]. Other possible sources of stress that might have significant effect on the health conditions of asthma victims were not included in the investigation. In addition, this study was confined only among eight purposely and conveniently selected study participants and does not cover the bigger number of samples to represent the entire population.

Conclusion

In view of the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

The continuous long exposure of one's head and breast within the GZ may eventually trigger symptoms of asthma and other respiratory health problems. In other words, GS is the major cause that triggers asthma.

The severity of person's asthma and the extent of symptoms that sit in is depending on the intensity of the geopathic situation, the amount of time spent there, and the nature and parts of human body directly exposed.

Asthma and other respiratory health problems become incurable and chronic when one's head and breast is remained exposed within GZ. However, it will gradually and normally disappear upon moving out from the stressed area. In other words, there is a complete insensitivity to any kind of treatment, or it is practically impossible to heal person who are affected by GS. Thus, moving person with chronic asthma from exposure within GZ is the simplest, practical and effective way to address the asthma health problems.

Asthma appears to be a disease of location. If a person is unluckily stayed for a longer time in a selected area whose heads and breasts were exposed within GZ he will most likely to acquire or develop asthma.

Finally, the findings revealed that asthma episodes are primarily triggered by GS. However, many people are severely affected by this illness because they are not aware of the occurrence GS in selected places and how it could be avoided. Unless the people acknowledge the existence GS and its adverse effect on their health the exact cause and cure for asthma will remain a mystery.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusions, the following are recommended:

The researcher, therefore, deemed it necessary to disseminate information on the existence of GS and its adverse effect on human health. It was proven to the satisfaction of the medical profession over 80 years ago, in millions of cases ever since, and in the present study that GS triggers asthma and even made asthma victims worse. Providing the knowledge on the nature of GS and its link to asthma and how it could be avoided may minimize if not totally eradicate the asthma health problems in our society. A research seminars, fora or symposia on the subject may be conducted for the said purpose.

The adage, which states that "an ounce of prevention is better than a pound of cure", aptly apply to GS health related problems. GS has been found to be the major factors that cause asthma and made it worse. Likewise, it is of evident that long exposure of one's body within GZ will lower immune system and ability to fight against viruses or infections. Until a person

is moved away within the GS zone their capacity to heal is not possible. Thus, avoiding from exposure from within GZ is the simplest, practical and effective way to address the asthma health problems.

In many European countries, Germany and Austria in particular, one of the first questions the doctor may ask is about the location of their bed and how long have they been sleeping there. These questions are routinely asked not only by several thousand doctors, but also many cancer specialist hospitals will recommend a Geopathic Surveyor as they are often called to investigate their home before deciding on a course of therapy or reaching for the prescription pad. The search using both dowsing methods to locate geopathic energies to determine whether their illness is linked to GS. If so, they were advised on how to avoid or eliminate these harmful energies from their home. So they stand a better chance of responding to any treatment given. Thus, in the effective handling of asthma health problems, doctors should work in close cooperation with the specialists in biological geophysics or dowsers, who are able to detect the dangerous GZ in the patient's homes.

GS has been always neglected and ignored because most of the people are unaware of its occurrence in certain location and how it could be detected. Awareness can lead to action to resolve the problem by removing himself from the zone to bring vast improvements in their health. Likewise, the use of dowsing tools in locating GZ has been proven as consistent, reliable, accurate and quick method. A program or training may be established to effectively disseminate information on the existence of GS in selected area, how it could be easily detected and avoided. Thus, a conduct of intensive training or seminar on the use of dowsing rods in locating the crossings of earth grids where GZ is found is a must for said purpose.

It is imperative that hospital beds of patients who are suffering from asthma be surveyed in order to avoid the adverse effect of GS on their health. It was confirmed in this study that GS triggers asthma and even made asthma victims worse. Likewise, it is of evident that it is difficult or impossible to treat asthma patients who are affected by GS because their capacity to heal is impaired. Hence, it is imperative among hospitals to have their beds be freed from GS for them to effectively treat the asthma health problems of their patients.

In many European countries having a survey for GS before buying a house is automatically undertaken through the services of GS surveyor. In this way they could ensure that the place where they stay most of the time is not affected by GS. Thus, a survey of GS be first undertaken prior to rent, buy or construct a house or office to avoid adverse effect of GS among occupants.

Equally this approach should be used in hospitals, nursery schools, kindergartens, schools where people stay in the same place for a long time. All these measures will allow to reduce sharply the risk of diseases induced of the GZ, to conserve the health of people, to increase the productivity of every worker and to recover the sick people.

To further validate the findings of the present investigation, the researcher recommends replication to other fields or groups, particularly among the medical practitioners. In this way, knowledge or awareness of the existence of GS and its effect on human health be further validated, established and widely disseminated.

References

1. Global Asthma Report (2014). [Link: https://goo.gl/3BH2w](https://goo.gl/3BH2w)
2. Health US News (2017) Asthma. [Link: https://goo.gl/WmJfEL](https://goo.gl/WmJfEL)
3. Bermington-Castro J (2016) What is asthma? [Link: https://goo.gl/Q2HbOL](https://goo.gl/Q2HbOL)
4. Quirce S, Bobola I, Barranco P (2012) Emerging drugs for asthma. *Expert Opin Emerg Drugs* 17: 219-237. [Link: https://goo.gl/Dn3EuV](https://goo.gl/Dn3EuV)
5. Environmental Protection Agency (2017) Asthma. [Link: https://goo.gl/q7ZZJY](https://goo.gl/q7ZZJY)
6. Case A (2013) Asthma solved naturally: The surprising underlying causes and hundreds strategies to beat asthma. Wilmington, Delaware, USA: Logical Books. [Link: https://goo.gl/aoSFJn](https://goo.gl/aoSFJn)
7. Adedeji A A (2007) Electromagnetism and your home. The facts Episteme Books. 164-168. [Link: https://goo.gl/FRJkna](https://goo.gl/FRJkna)
8. Derek JC (1994) The effect of Geopathic stress among building occupants. *Renew Energy* 5: 993-996. [Link: https://goo.gl/2CcEH5](https://goo.gl/2CcEH5)
9. Cramer G (1996) Advanced research on atmospheric ions and respiratory problems. [Link: https://goo.gl/bJd2Lz](https://goo.gl/bJd2Lz)
10. Ledford DK (2015) Ozone and negative ion generator. American academy of allergy Asthma and Immunology. [Link: https://goo.gl/DpVJIS](https://goo.gl/DpVJIS)
11. Chawla P (2002) Six stages of GS. [Link: https://goo.gl/wXa6c4](https://goo.gl/wXa6c4)
12. Craddock P (2005) Health and wise. [Link: https://goo.gl/hOKT0m](https://goo.gl/hOKT0m)
13. Tambade PS, Aghav SD (2015) Investigating effect off GS on health parameters in young healthy volunteers. *International J of Chemical Science* 4: 28-34. [Link: https://goo.gl/RKbWne](https://goo.gl/RKbWne)
14. Overman JR, Britton D (2014) Dangers associated with geopathic stress.
15. Gordon R (2005) Are you sleeping in a safe place? 130 Gipsy Hill London SE USA. [Link: https://goo.gl/72Y5xj](https://goo.gl/72Y5xj)
16. Orgone Energy (2013) Geopathic stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/aJ14ip](https://goo.gl/aJ14ip)
17. Anderson S, Spurling S (2012) In the mind of a master. Universe: Bloomington, USA. [Link: https://goo.gl/krggQ5](https://goo.gl/krggQ5)
18. Convocar J (2012) Freeing persons from GS zone: How are they now? In: IAMURE International of Health Education. [Link: https://goo.gl/39z44B](https://goo.gl/39z44B)
19. Kharat AG (2000) Empirical and theoretical investigation on built environment. Ph. D. Thesis, university of Pune. [Link: https://goo.gl/hDgmPu](https://goo.gl/hDgmPu)
20. Gerhard WH (2005) Biomedical evidence of influence of geopathic stress on the human body: Scientifically traceable effects and ways of harmonization. *Forsch Complementarmed Klass Natruheilkd* 12: 315-327. [Link: https://goo.gl/ufzUMd](https://goo.gl/ufzUMd)
21. Bergsmann O, Artmann P, Bergsmann J, Birkmayer J, Friedrich M, et al. (1989) Pathogene Standorteinflüsse, inhaltlich und personell wie folgt mitgearbeitet, Institut für Angewandte Forschung Und Produktmarketing, Porzellangasse 60: 158.
22. Dubrov AP (2008) Geopathic zones and oncological disease. [Link: https://goo.gl/8I8oCY](https://goo.gl/8I8oCY)
23. Brandmaier W (2013) Geopathic stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/ELAaK9](https://goo.gl/ELAaK9)
24. Hacker GW, Pawlak E, Pauser G, Tichy G, Jell H, et al. (2005) Biomedical evidence of influence of geopathic zones on the human body: scientifically traceable effects and ways of harmonization. *Forsch Complementarmed Klass Naturheilkd* 12: 315-327. [Link: https://goo.gl/EA2TnX](https://goo.gl/EA2TnX)
25. Convocar J (2015) Staying over and moving away from GS zone: A case study. *Peak Journal of Public Health and Management* 3: 18-19. [Link: https://goo.gl/mXiS84](https://goo.gl/mXiS84)
26. Creightmore R (2009) Geopathic stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/QZ7YqQ](https://goo.gl/QZ7YqQ)
27. Jacobs R (2009) Geopathic stress.
28. Freshwater D (1997) Geopathic stress. *Complementary Therapies in Nursing and Midwifery* 3: 160-162. [Link: https://goo.gl/ZB4GgJ](https://goo.gl/ZB4GgJ)
29. Saunders T (2003) Health hazards and electromagnetic fields. *Complementary Therapies in Nursing and Midwifery* 9: 191-197. [Link: https://goo.gl/cLb7q5](https://goo.gl/cLb7q5)
30. Lee L (2001) Childhood conditions. [Link: https://goo.gl/6ywrV0](https://goo.gl/6ywrV0)
31. Li D, Chen H, Odouli R (2011) Maternal exposure to magnetic fields during pregnancy in relation to the risk of asthma in offspring. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med* 165: 945-950. [Link: https://goo.gl/Whx4TS](https://goo.gl/Whx4TS)
32. Asthma Foundation (2016) Common asthma triggers. [Link: https://goo.gl/XUMxXs](https://goo.gl/XUMxXs)
33. Web MD (2017) Asthma Symptoms. [Link: https://goo.gl/OMGmkt](https://goo.gl/OMGmkt)
34. National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (2017) What are the signs and symptoms of asthma? [Link: https://goo.gl/JK9d6e](https://goo.gl/JK9d6e)
35. More BM (2014) An experimental study on water dowsing. *International Journal of Research and Innovations in Earth Science* 1: 17-19. [Link: https://goo.gl/qHJiMg](https://goo.gl/qHJiMg)
36. Harvalik Z V (1978) Anatomical localization of human detection of weak electromagnetic radiation: Experiments with dowsers. *Physiol Chem Phys* 10: 525-534 [Link: https://goo.gl/hDz7cl](https://goo.gl/hDz7cl)
37. Dharmadhikari N, Kharat AG, Pimplikar S (2010) [Professor Benedict] A study of geopathic stress using light interface techniques. *Research Communications – Current Science* 98: 695-697.
38. Bachler K (1989) Earth radiation. *Word Asters Ltd* 10: 34-35. [Link: https://goo.gl/UCchxk](https://goo.gl/UCchxk)
39. Betz H D (1995) Unconventional water detection: Field test of the dowsing technique in dry zones, Part I and II. *J Sci Explor* 9: 1-2. [Link: https://goo.gl/Dq7PO0](https://goo.gl/Dq7PO0)
40. Graves T (2008) Geopathic stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/SNSXak](https://goo.gl/SNSXak)
41. Earth Transition (2008) Geopathic stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/njH5pL](https://goo.gl/njH5pL)
42. Randi J (2012) Dowsing: Science or pseudoscience. James Randi Educational Foundation. [Link: https://goo.gl/jgg09g](https://goo.gl/jgg09g)
43. Readers and Root Workers (2009) Geopathic stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/KqtKvr](https://goo.gl/KqtKvr)
44. Zimbio (2008) Environment. [Link: https://goo.gl/4EMeQz](https://goo.gl/4EMeQz)
45. Anderson S, Anderson S (2008) Stages of GS. [Link: https://goo.gl/0gq8y7](https://goo.gl/0gq8y7)
46. Wharton N (2013) Are you concerned with Electro-pollution. [Link: https://goo.gl/ucaJSf](https://goo.gl/ucaJSf)
47. Moore A (2013) Geopathic stress and earth acupuncture. [Link: https://goo.gl/OgD7IN](https://goo.gl/OgD7IN)

48. Reynolds FJ (2009) Your Essence is magnetic. Ideal Publishing: New York, USA. [Link: https://goo.gl/Iehccm](https://goo.gl/Iehccm)
49. Ledford DK (2015) Ozone and negative ion generator. American academy of allergy. In: Asthma and Immunology. [Link: https://goo.gl/FrPj1h](https://goo.gl/FrPj1h)
50. Rahi GS (2017) Positive Ion Poisoning. Physical Laws and social Orders. [Link: https://goo.gl/mSVeKD](https://goo.gl/mSVeKD)
51. Thurnell-Read J (2016) Geopathic stress and subtle energy. Life work potential 8: 11-24. [Link: https://goo.gl/rqHJvw](https://goo.gl/rqHJvw)
52. EMR Labs (2011) Positive Ions versus Negative Ions. [Link: https://goo.gl/UUHNqQ](https://goo.gl/UUHNqQ)
53. Havas M, Olstad A (2008) Power quality affects teacher wellbeing and student behavior in three Minnesota Schools. Sci Total Environ 402: 157-162. [Link: https://goo.gl/3CfDKH](https://goo.gl/3CfDKH)
54. Nambudripad DS (2003) Say to Good-Bye to series. Buena Park, CA: Delta Publishing.
55. Riggs R (2012) Geopathic Stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/Swb3vl](https://goo.gl/Swb3vl)
56. Korotkov K (2013) Energy fields electrophotonic analysis in humans and nature. [Link: https://books.google.com.ph/books?](https://books.google.com.ph/books?) [Link: https://goo.gl/iTTyhO](https://goo.gl/iTTyhO)
57. Natural Therapy Center (2014) Geopathic stress and its effect on health. [Link: https://goo.gl/zCvg77](https://goo.gl/zCvg77)
58. Rocka J, Creightmore RH (2014) Geopathic stress. [Link: https://goo.gl/750L1X](https://goo.gl/750L1X)
59. Kopschina A, Daun U (1994) Die krankmachende Wirkung Geopathischer Belastung. [Link: https://goo.gl/8gwKPH](https://goo.gl/8gwKPH)
60. Poddar A, Rana S (2014) Effect of geopathic stress and its correction on human body and machinery breakdown. Landmark Research J 1: 41-45. [Link: https://goo.gl/tsJGPe](https://goo.gl/tsJGPe)
61. Tietze HW (1995) Earthrays and manmade pollution. [Link: https://goo.gl/b0nTRZ](https://goo.gl/b0nTRZ)
62. Swiss Harmony (2017) Earth Rays. [Link: https://goo.gl/A02yKR](https://goo.gl/A02yKR)
63. Aghav AA, Tambade PS (2015) Investigating effects of GS on health parameters in young healthy volunteers. International Journal of Chemical and Physical Sciences 4: 28-34. [Link: https://goo.gl/AaaLC4](https://goo.gl/AaaLC4)
64. Spurling S (2015) What is geopathic stress and why we care about it? [Link: https://goo.gl/GEZnls](https://goo.gl/GEZnls)
65. Dubrov AP (2008) Geopathic zones and oncological disease. [Link: https://goo.gl/baBB3U](https://goo.gl/baBB3U)
66. Newerla B (2010) Protect yourself from electromagnetic pollution by using crystals. [Link: https://goo.gl/zekXfg](https://goo.gl/zekXfg)